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New records of Alucitidae and Pterophoridae species from Crete (Lepidoptera)

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Abstract. This study reports collection and observation data for eight Pterophoridae and one Alucitidae species from the island of Crete. The bionomic and geographical distribution of each species is given. *Megalorhipidia leucodactylus* (Fabricius, 1794) is a new species for Crete. The wing habitus and genitalia structure of several species are described.

Keywords. New faunistic data, bionomy, distribution, remarks on species.

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Introduction

With an area of 8,261 km² Crete (Kreta) is the largest island in Greece and the fifth-largest Mediterranean island, stretching about 260 km from east to west and between 12 and 57 km from north to south. It is mountainous, reaching 2,456 m on Mt. Psiloritis in the centre of the island. In the west are the Lefka Ori mountains with 43 peaks above 2,000 m. There are also several other mountain ranges. Crete is part of the Aegean Sea & East Mediterranean Mixed Forests Bioregion.

The island has a Mediterranean climate, with warm summers and cold winters. Most precipitation occurs during winter, falling as snow in the mountains. From May to October there is almost no rain.

The warm and dry low plains have an average annual temperature of about 17–19°C, with total rainfall of less than 300 mm in the southeastern part of the island. Cold and humid higher elevations have an annual average temperature of about 9–13°C, with total rainfall of up to 1,400 mm. Crete, halfway between Europe and Africa, has a unique flora. The wide altitudinal range of this ecoregion has resulted in several forest zones. The lowest elevations are distinguished by sclerophyllous evergreen and semi-deciduous oak forests, "maquis" of carob (*Ceretonia siliqua*), Phoenician juniper (*Juniperus phoenicea*), tree-spurge (*Euphorbia dendroides*), prickly juniper (*Juniperus oxycarpa*), olive (*Olea europaea*), myrtle (*Backhousia citriodora*), strawberry tree (*Arbutus unedo*), tree heath (*Erica arborea*), heather (*Erica manipuliflora*) and many other species.

At medium altitudes, mesophyllous pine forests (*Pinus brutia*) and holly oak (*Quercus coccifera*) woodlands are widely spread. The higher elevations host impressive cypress (*Cupressus sempervirens*) woodlands, where the endemic evergreen maple (*Acer sempervirens*) frequently grows. In the high mountains, extensive thorny cushion shrublands occur and support many endemic species.

Throughout history, Crete's forests have been dramatically reduced. Barren land, with thin soils and degraded shrublands, are the predominant features of the island. During Classical and Medieval times, Crete was an important shipbuilding centre and timber exporting country. Cypress timber was once a very valuable resource. The island has seen great fluctuations in population and prosperity, resulting in a long history of abuse of timber resources. Overgrazing and the setting of fires to produce fresh grassland have contributed to the transformation of

Fig 1. Geographical location of the island of Crete

Fig. 2. Topographical and hydrographic map of the island of Crete

Fig 3. Vegetation map of Crete Winter pastures and sheep farming areas encompass cultivation of phrygana, maquis, and oak forests. Summer pastures extend over phrygana, maquis, forests and subalpine shrubland (after Kypriotakis et al. 1996; partially modified | by Fazekas I.)

large areas of mature forests into degraded shrublands. Today, at least 50% of the land surface is used for grazing sheep and goats.

Many-plumed moths (Alucitidae) are a small family with currently over 200 described species in nine genera. Adults are active in deep shade or may be crepuscular. Where the early stages are known, the larvae are borers or gall makers. Food plant records occur in Bignoniaceae, Caprifoliaceae, Compositae, Dipsacaceae, Labiatae, and Rubiaceae. The larvae live inside the flowers and stems and often cause swellings. The pupae are usually found in webs on the

ground. The imagines fly typically at night. Most species settle in tree hollows, cracks in tree bark, cellars, cave walls, corridors, and attics of buildings.

According to https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_Lepidoptera_of_Greece#Alucitidae, seven species of Alucitidae are known as Crete as follows:

Alucita desmodactyla Zeller, 1847
Alucita hexadactyla (Linnaeus, 1758)
Alucita huebneri Wallengren, 1859
Alucita major (Rebel, 1906)
Alucita palodactyla Zeller, 1847
Alucita pectinata Scholz & Jackh, 1994
Alucita zonodactyla Zeller, 1847

Worldwide, nearly 1500 species of Pterophoridae have been described, in more than 90 genera. Gielis (1993) reported 133 species in his European book. Since then, the number of species has increased. Potentially, there are probably 140 species on the European continent. Fazekas (2021) reported 91 species in his book on the Balkan Peninsula. The fauna of Pterophoridae of Greece and its archipelago is less well-known. Detailed, comprehensive, systematic studies have not yet been carried out. Our knowledge is limited to various data reporting, and faunistic studies. The number of Pterophoridae species recorded from the island of Crete is about 70, but this number is uncertain.

Material and methods

The specimens were collected by the second author and are housed in his collection. Genital examinations were carried out by the first author. Specimens were dissected following standard techniques (Robinson 1976), and the genitalia structures of the additional male and female were embedded in Euparal on permanent slides. The genitalia of the copulating pair was dissected and documented step by step in alcohol, using the mechanical fixation methods described by Wanke & Rajaei (2018), Wanke et al. (2019) and Wanke et al. (2021).

List of species

Note: Species names are given in alphabetical order.

Alucitidae

Alucita desmodactyla Zeller, 1847

Examined material: 1 female, wingspan 19 mm, Crete, *Quercus coccifera* Forest Above Lochria, Mt. Ida, 08.11.2018, leg. H. Edmunds, gen. prep. et det. I. Fazekas No. 3531; 1 female, Crete, Agios Georgios, 05.11.2021, leg. H. Edmunds, gen. prep. et det. I. Fazekas No. 3517.

Bionomy. Adults fly from the end of July till early December, hibernate, and reappear in spring from March to June. Recorded foodplants *Stachys recta* L. and *S. alpina* (in flowers) and *S. sylvatica* (Fazekas 2010, Gielis 2003, Schwarz 1953).

Distribution. A species is known from the Western Palaearctic from Iran, Armenia to Tunisia, Spain: Armenia, Austria, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Crete, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Iran, Macedonia, Moldavia, Poland, Romania, Russia (Volga region, the Russian Caucasus), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Tunisia, Ukraine. It is probably an expansive holomediterranean faunal element, but this needs further investigation.

Remarks. Described from Austria (Wien), locally distributed in Central and Southern Europe. According to Šumpich & Skyva (2014) new species for Greece: Peloponnes, Kertézi, 1000 m. The bionomics and geographical distribution of *Alucita* species are poorly understood. The family has approximately 195–200 described species, with representatives on all continents and climate zones. Known hostplants belong to Asteraceae, Caprifoliaceae and Lamiaceae (Gielis 2003).

Pterophoridae

2. *Agdistis bigoti* Arenberger, 1996 | Figs 4–6.

Examined material: 1 female, wingspan 22 mm, Crete, Comos Beach, Timbaki, 14.04.2021, leg. H. Edmunds, gen. prep. et det. I. Fazekas No. 3528; 1 male, Crete, Ithamos, Nr. Vai, Bast-coast. 08.11.2022, leg. H. Edmunds, gen. prep. et det. I. Fazekas No. 3522.

Bionomy. According to Gielis (1996), adult flies from May to August. According to recent observations, the moth flies as early as April and can be collected as late as November. It is probably a two-generation species. The larvae and food plants are not yet known. It may be an endemic species on the island of Crete, but this needs to be confirmed by further research in the wider geographical area.

Distribution. Only in Crete. Other sites according to Arenberger (1996): Matala, Kuphoni, Chersoneseos.

Remarks. According to Arenberger (1996) due to the extremely poor state of preservation of all specimens examined, a more exact description of the external characteristics of this species is not possible. However, there is no doubt about the species legitimacy of *Agdistis bigoti* because the genital apparatus in both sexes is unmistakable. The male genital is very conspicuous by the forked process of the 8th sternite. Only *Singularia walsinghami* (Fernald, 1898) and *Agdistis bifurcatus* (Agenjo, 1952) have similar sternite cones, but in both these are forked after 1/2 of their length. In *A. bigoti*, from the base of two arms, a further two arms are present. *A. bigoti* is another species of the „frankeniae” group. This is confirmed by their female genital apparatus. Antrum in ventral view caudally overly broad, orally tapering abruptly after 3/4 abruptly tapering, strongly sclerotized. The membranous corpus bursae are only about 1/4 longer than the antrum. In the paper, detailed photos of the male and female reproductive organs are shown. Highlighting the most important specific markers. The wing habitus is also shown, as no similar representation is known in previous publications.

3. *Agdistis tamaricis* (Zeller, 1847) | Fig. 7.

Examined material: 1 female, wingspan 20 mm, Crete, Comos Beach, Timbaki, 07.07.2018, leg. H. Edmunds, gen. prep. et det. I. Fazekas No. 3515.

Bionomy. Flight period in two generations from March to September, from the plains up to an altitude of 1700 m. Larvae on the leaves of *Tamarix dioica*, *T. gallica*, *T. smyrnensis*, *T. aphylla*, *T. canariensis*, *T. africana*, *T. gennanica* and *Myricaria germanica*.

Distribution. Widespread in the Palaearctic and Afrotropical regions.

Remarks. This species is absent or unrecorded from vast areas of Central Asia, or populations are there highly fragmented. Its schematic, bicentric distribution is shown on the map North of the Balkan Peninsula, in Hungary, Fazekas (1997) studied the occurrence of the species, the food plant and habitats in detail. He found that the species was introduced into the country with horticultural crops. Likely, *A. tamaricis* is not native to several European regions but is an adventive species. It is still unrecorded in several countries in the Balkans, but its occurrence can be expected. The adults are externally similar to other *Agdistis* species, and dissection is recommended for identification.

3. *Emmelina monodactyla* (Linnaeus, 1758) |

Examined material: 1 male, wingspan 19 mm, Crete, Agios Georgios, 08.07.2018, leg. H. Edmunds, gen. prep. et det. I. Fazekas No. 3530; 1 male, wingspan 20 mm, 2 male Crete, Agios Georgios, 14.10.2019, leg. H. Edmunds, gen. prep. et det. I. Fazekas No. 3519.

Bionomy. Flight period throughout the year. Larvae polyphagous, recorded on *Convolvulus arvensis*, *C. microphyllus*, *C. cantabrica*, *C. althaeoides*, *C. floridus*, *C. subacaulis*, *Calystegia soldanella*, *C. sepium*, *C. spithamea*, *Chenopodium* spp., *Atriplex* spp., *Ipomoea purpurea*, *I. batatas*, *I. hispida*, *I. niger* and *Datura stramonium*. It favours typical host plant habitats such as dry grasslands, roadsides, weedy areas, forest edges, scrub edges, rocky grasslands, steppe slopes, as well as semi-arid and wet habitats, groves, and agricultural and kitchen gardens.

Distribution. A wide-ranging species, mainly known from the western Palaearctic. In the south, it is found in North Africa and Saudi Arabia. It is found in southern Siberia and central Asia, as well as in China and northern India. Elsewhere, it occurs in the Nearctic, in Canada

Figs 4–7. *Agdistis bigoti*, 4. adult; 5. male genitalia; 6. the abdomen of a female, in lateral view; *Agdistis tamaricis*, 7. adult (the wing apex is slightly damaged).

and U.S.A, in Neotropical Venezuela and Mexico in Afrotropical Kenya (Gielis, 2003), in Oriental India and the Philippines. Probably an introduced species outside the Palaearctic.

Remarks. In January, the author collected specimens on a tree trunk at -19° Celsius. At room temperature, they were flying within an hour. Specimens stored in the freezer for several days were not damaged.

4. *Hellinsia carphodactyla* (Hübner, [1813])

Examined material: 1 male, wingspan 18 mm, Crete, Agios Georgios, 24.11.2021, leg. H. Edmunds, gen. prep. et det. I. Fazekas No. 3518.

Bionomy. Flight period from May to September in two generations, Larvae oligophagous on *Inula conyza*, *I. bifrons*, *I. montana*, *I. hirta*, *Dittrichia viscosa*, *Bupthalmum salicifolium* and *Carlina vulgaris*, The first brood feeds in stems at leaf axils, the second brood bores in flower heads and into receptacle and stem. *Carlina vulgaris* is now quite common in roadsides and ruderal habitats, even in urban areas. It is an invasive species in Australia, and very resistant to adverse conditions and degraded environments. The widespread distribution of this host plant is not correlated with the presence of the moth, which inhabits forest edges, sparse dry forests, steppe meadows, and rocky grasslands. from the lowlands to 1600–1800 m. in the mountains.

Distribution. *Hellinsia carphodactyla* is known from the Kazan region of Russia, through the Balkans and into Europe, as far as the British Isles. It is not found in Scandinavia. There is an old record in the literature from Morocco (Bigot 1964).

Remarks. According to Gielis (1996) *H. carphodactyla* shows considerable variation in size. Specimens from cooler climates are larger than those from warmer areas. We have only seen one specimen from the island of Crete: a wingspan of 18 mm. Further observations are needed.

5. *Lantanophaga pusillidactylus* (Walker, 1864) | Figs 8–11.

Examined material: 1 female, wingspan 12 mm, Crete, Agios Georgios, 16.09.2014, leg. H. Edmunds, gen. prep. et det. I. Fazekas No. 3516.

Bionomy. The larvae are known to feed on various *Lantana* species, but its main food plant is *Lantana camara*. They feed inside flowers or tunnel around the base of the flower for seven to ten days and pupate in the flower clusters. The development time from egg to adult is about fourteen days. All three records of *L. pusillidactylus* were found near *Lantana camara*. According to Gielis (1996), the adults are on the wing in July and again between September and December. According to Agius (2017), the Maltese records consolidate the flight period to the last 6 months of the year, possibly *L. pusillidactylus* has multiple generations during the year.

Distribution. *L. pusillidactylus* is also found throughout Mexico and the Caribbean.

Remarks. In Europe and the Mediterranean area, until 1996 the species was only known from Morocco, Madeira, and the Canary Islands. In 1997, it was recorded for the first time in mainland Europe in Spain (King 2000). A few years later, the species was found in Italy (Bella & Marchese 2007), Sicily (D'urso et al., 2008), and Portugal (Corley et al., 2008). Most probably *L. pusillidactylus* was introduced in various countries with the importation of *Lantana* plants.

6. *Megalorhipidia leucodactylus* (Fabricius, 1794) | Figs 12–13. | **New for Crete.**

Examined material: 1 male, wingspan 12 mm, Crete, Agios Georgios, 02.11.2021, leg. H. Edmunds, gen. prep. et det. I. Fazekas No. 3514.

Diagnosis. Forewings cleft from halfway, yellow-brown. Markings brown. A small discal spot and poorly defined transverse bands on the first lobe at base and middle, and a faint dark area near the apex. Fringes yellow-brown, grey-brown at the dark spots and along the costa of the second lobe opposite the dark markings, on dorsum of the second lobe dark, mixed with isolated black scales. Underside dark brown, paler along the costa and towards the apex of both lobes.

Hindwings brown, fringes dark brown. An indistinct scale-tooth in the middle of the dorsum of the third lobe. The underside of first and second lobes brown, third lobe yellow-brown.

Figs 8–11.
Lantanophaga pusillidactylus;
8. adult;
9. female genitalia;
10. habitat in the area of Agios Georgios;
11. schematic geographical distribution in Southern Europe and Africa.

Venous scales ferruginous, in a double row, proceeding in a single row (see Gielis 2006).

Bionomy. Recorded larvae feed on seeds of *Boerhavia diffusa* and *B. repens* (Nyctaginaceae). Other recorded hostplants include *Acacia neovernicosa* (Fabaceae), *Boerhavia coccinea*, *B. erecta*, *B. chinensis*, *Commicarpus tuberosus*, *Okenia hypogaea* (Nyctaginaceae), *Amaranthus* spp. (Amaranthaceae), *Mimosa tenuiflora* (Fabaceae), *Lagenaria siceraria* (Cucurbitaceae), and *Scaevola frutescens* (Goodeniaceae). According to Arenberger (2002) larvae feed by gnawing on the immature fruits of the food plant. Flight period: All year round, altitude up to 2300 m. Data on larvae food from Europe are missing. The larvae can be identified by the following description: length about 6 mm, yellowish grey with a reddish tinge, midline narrow, slightly darker than the base colour, and head black.

According to Matthews (2008), the pupa reaching about 8 mm in length, is light green and tan to brown, with darker markings on the head, thorax and appendages, and covered with rows of short to minute recurved setae. They are fastened to the slender branched inflorescence stalks of the host, anchored to a silken pad by two patches of hooked setae on the ventral surface of the caudal segment. The cast larval skin is stretched out behind and remains attached to the plant, as opposed to being bunched up and falling away as in most other genera.

Distribution. Its geographical distribution is huge. It has been observed in the following biogeographical regions: Palaearctic, Afrotropical, Neotropical, Australasian, and Pacific. Native ranges are Pantropical and Circumpolar regions. **New for Crete.**

Remarks. According to Gielis (1996) this species, described from Central America and widespread in the tropics and subtropics, also occurs in southern Spain; Fauna Europaea follows him in this. Arenberger (2002) can only refer to Gielis (1996) for Europe, so he has not seen any specimens here.

Lopez-Vaamonde et al. (2010: 608) write: "*M. leucodactylus* has a circum-tropical distribution and has established populations in Sicily (Bella and Ferrauo 2005) and Israel. It has also been recorded in Spain, but its presence there needs confirmation (Gielis, pers. comm.)." Vives Moreno (2014: 195, 766) then mentions the species only for the Canary Islands, explaining, "Especie citada de las Islas Canarias, España, concretamente de Fuerteventura (Arenberger & Baéz 2011)." An occurrence in southern Spain is thus denied. Arenberger & Baez (2011: 86) wrote about their report from the Canary Islands: "Fuerteventura: Tarajalejo, 15-30.4.1996, M. u. E. Arenberger. Distribution: Widespread in tropical and subtropical areas. A discovery for the Canary Islands!" Thus, whether the species is established there - and if so, since when - remains unclear for the time being; however, the establishment is likely.

Nel & Varenne (2019) report the species for the first time in France (1 specimen on the beach near Marseille, Les Goudes, Parc National des Calanques, on 18 October 2018).

So far, no relevant observational data have been found for the island of Crete. It is therefore assumed to be a new species on the island.

7. *Merrifieldia malacodactylus* (Zeller, 1847)

Examined material: 1 female, wingspan 14 mm, Crete, Agios Georgios, 09.05.2012, leg. H. Edmunds, gen. prep. et det. I. Fazekas No. 3524.

Bionomy. Flight period in three generations, between March and October. In central Europe and higher mountain areas, between 1000–2500 m, only two generations. Larvae on shoots and flowers of *Origanum vulgare*, *Thymus vulgaris*, *T. herba-barona*, *Lavandula stoechas*, *L. angustifolia*, *L. latifolia*, *Calamintha nepeta*, *Rosmarinus officinalis*, *Salvia lavandulifolia* and *Nepeta nepetellae*. Many of the host plants are cultivated, which helps the moth to colonise new areas. Habitat dry margins of oak woodland, scrub, karst scrub, rocky grasslands, and steep slopes, but also in nurseries and domestic flowerbeds.

Distribution. Extends from Afghanistan through western Asia to the whole of southern Europe. It is also found locally in North Africa and the Arabian Peninsula. In southern central Europe, it is very local and rare. According to Fazekas (2000) the northern limit of its range is the central part of Hungary, the Velence Mountains.

Remarks. *M. malacodactylus* is variable, and several local forms have been described as separate species. Therefore, there are many synonyms (see Arenberger, 1996, Gielis, 2003). For the identification of specimens, it is important to examine the genitalia. It is described by Aren-

Figs 12–13. *Megalorhipidia leucodactylus*; **12a.** adult; **12b.** pupa, dorsal view (Matthews 2008); **13.** male genitalia. The species its geographical distribution is huge. It has been observed in the following biogeographical regions: Palearctic, Afrotropical, Neotropical, Australasian, and Pacific. Native ranges are Pantropical and Circumpolar regions.

Figs 14– 16. *Stangeia siceliota*; **14.** adult; *Wheeleria ivae*; **15.** adult; **16.** habitat in Mt. Ida; **17.** rocky, highly barren, xerothermic habitat on Mount Ida. Typical habitat of the *Alucita desmodactyla* species.

berger and other authors as a Mediterranean fauna element, but in the opinion of this author, it is more a Holomediterranean-Iranian faunal element. Further investigation is needed (Fazekas, 2000).

8. *Stangeia siceliota* (Zeller, 1847) | Fig. 14.

Examined material: 1 male, wingspan 12 mm, Crete, Agios Georgios, 08.09.2014, leg. H. Edmunds, gen. prep. et det. I. Fazekas No. 3526; 1 female, Crete, Comos Beach, Timbaki, 07.07.2018, leg. H. Edmunds, gen. prep. et det. I. Fazekas No. 3520; 1 male, Crete, Comos Beach, Timbaki, 14.11.2021, leg. H. Edmunds, gen. prep. et det. I. Fazekas No. 3529.

Bionomy. The number of generations and the exact flight time are not yet known. Specimens have been collected from March to November, which indicates that there are at least three generations. Larvae on shoots of *Cistus monspeliensis*, *C. albidus*, *C. salviaefolius*, *Sanguisorba* spp., *Dittrichia viscosa*, *D. graveolens*, *Helichrysum angustifolium*, *Ononis natrix*, *O. reclinata* and *Sarcopoterium spinosum*, *Stangeia siceliota* is predominantly a species of Mediterranean-type shrubs, thickets, and forest edges. It occurs in sandy landscapes, steppe meadows, southern rocky grasslands, and desert environments. It has adapted to the most extreme ecological niches. It has colonized from the lowlands to the high mountain ranges up to 3000 m. In Dalmatia Orno-Quercetum, in Greece *Ostryo-Carpinion-aegeicum*, *Oleo-Ceratonion* vegetation zones are not uncommon. In Bulgaria, it occurs very locally in *Quercetum frainetto-cerris* associations.

Distribution. According to Arenberger (2002), a Mediterranean species, whose distribution limits are Switzerland and Hungary in the north and extend as far as China in the east. In the author's opinion, it is not a Mediterranean species, but a multi-centred faunal element of southern Eurasia. The area of distribution of Central- and South Asian populations, including Saudi Arabia, Yemen, Turkmenistan, Iraq, Iran and Afghanistan is not yet clear. A rough map of the known distribution of the region in earlier work (see Fazekas 1999, Figure 6) is presented here.

Remarks. The occurrence in Bosnia-Herzegovina has yet to be confirmed. According to Fazekas (1999), *S. siceliota* is concentrated in southern Europe and the Middle East, areas with Mediterranean climates, having warm summers. The winter has a mean annual temperature exceeding 14° C and the coldest month has a mean temperature above 4° C. Annual rainfall is generally between 500 and 1000 mm per year, and the natural vegetation cover is dominated by hardy evergreen forest. In France and Switzerland, *S. siceliota* occurs in the southern part of the temperate zone where winters are mild. In the Carpathian Basin, the temperate steppe vegetation reaches fragments of the northern border of its range (Fót, Somlyó Hill). In the southwestern mountain ranges of Arabia, in the tropical dry savannah climate, the short-grass, dry, shrubby savannah in the Asir Mountains, Namas, 2000–2350 m.

9. *Wheeleria ivae* Kasy, 1960 | Fig. 15.

Examined material: 1 female, wingspan 20 mm, Crete, Agios Georgios, 08.09.2011, leg. H. Edmunds, gen. prep. et det. I. Fazekas No. 3523.

Bionomy. Flight period from May to September. Larvae on *Stachys iva*, *S. sylvatica* and *Betonica scardica*. Habitat stony slopes, dry meadows, roadsides, and sunny, dry rocky grasslands up from 400 to 2300–2400 m. Populations are scattered and at low density.

Distribution. Limited to the Balkans, Crete, Cyprus, Asia Minor and the Middle East (Lebanon and Syria).

Remarks. The ecology of the host plants and their distribution determine the presence of *W. ivae* in the region. According to Ball (1972), they grow on the mountain and subalpine meadows and scrub, on serpentine or limestone. Populations threatened by grazing, afforestation, and timber production.

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